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Qualitative Study on Application of Technological Innovations at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This paper dwelt on qualitative study on application of technological innovations at secondary school level of education in Nigeria: a systematic review. Over the years, teaching in schools has been done in the traditional way while learning by students and teachers alike was before now facilitated by traditional means. If the situation persists, how the nations' educational system can compete with the rest of the world is a mirage. Lately, the narratives have changed with advancement in technology which have permeated every aspect of human life and economy as well. It thus created room for convenience, attractiveness and without no monopoly of knowledge as was the case in the past. The duo concepts of teaching and learning are interwoven and complex but central to the business of the educational system of any nation, including Nigeria. Teaching and learning are the embodiment of the nations' educational system upon which other sectors of the economy relied upon. It is also the driving force upon which the objectives of our schools are accomplished. The paper therefore discuss the concepts of technology, curriculum innovation, teaching and learning; technological tools for teaching and learning in schools, use of technology in teaching and learning, importance of the use of technology in teaching and learning in schools and challenges to the use of technology in Nigerian schools. It further proffer solutions to the challenges identified such as provision of alternative source of power supply, provision of technological tools to teachers and students at subsidized rate, mandatory provision of technological tools before resumption to schools among others.

Keywords; Innovation, Learning, Schools, Teaching and Technology

Introduction

It is an understatement to say that technology is not a tool that can be applied to all areas of human endeavor especially in the teaching and learning processes at the secondary schools and extent to which her goals are achieved. This technology in question no doubt has replaced the traditional form of teaching and learning by teachers and students in schools. It is therefore a novelty idea which has transformed all activities at the nation's education system. The innovation brought about by its adoption, integration and use is inevitable to all human race as no one group or organization wants to remain static at a position for too long. This is no surprise why human beings on their part have tried on daily basis to acquire knowledge, skills and values of one form or another to better themselves, communities, the nation at large and improve quality of education at all levels. This type of education as being speculated can only be obtained through formal or informal education, depending on the choice more accessible by people and resources at their disposal.

Formal education can be obtained at the primary, secondary or tertiary institutions depending on the objectives of education being sought. These schools are like military barracks where students come in from time-to-time and leave at the expiration of their stay over there. One thing is thus certain, to learn under the tutelage of their teachers who have been professionally trained to do so. Though, teaching and learning at the secondary schools have slightly changed from what it used to be in the past. This is because teaching and learning processes in the 21st century is being facilitated through technology either online or offline and at ease for both the teachers and students alike. Without mincing words, it is a testament to technological advancement which has over the years transformed human society, making the world a global village as it is the situation in the present information age. Buttressing further, teacher - chalkboard method has hitherto facilitated what teachers do in the class before now while students on their part have relied heavily on copied lesson notes and available text books for

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their assignments. Far from this, the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have now become an integral part of every human society in today's world (Nwachukwu, 2006). This development has challenged the traditional role of the education sector in all human societies. Notably, secondary education is faced with the challenge of equipping the learners with technology and information literacy, problem solving skills, critical reasoning, and the ability to use digital technology in accessing and utilizing information for problem-solving in addition to knowledge of subject's content in class. Despite these challenges, the use of ICTs in Nigeria and other Africa countries are increasing and dramatically growing by the day. While there is a great deal of knowledge about how ICTs are being used in developed countries, there is no much information on how ICTs are being introduced into schools in developing countries including Nigeria (Beukes - Amiss and Chiware, 2006). Owing to this, it has become imperative to examine qualitative study on application of technological innovation at secondary school level of education in Nigeria: a systematic review.

Concepts of Technology, Teaching and Learning

Trio concepts of technology, teaching and learning have all been examined one after the other. The connection however, with them, is education advances with technology. Judging by the present reality today, it is crystal clear that the modern - day classroom needs are very different from the conventional classroom needs. This shows that technology provide maximum support for education through its dynamic, flexible and interactive content especially within the secondary education context. The application of educational technology in the classroom setting improves teaching - learning process and permits teachers as well as learners to interact as human beings in a climate where people control their environment for their own desired purposes. Classroom knowledge as provided for in the secondary schools are made more relevant and applicable to real world situations through the use of appropriate technology (Kwache, 2007). It also provides opportunities for personal learning plan as well as motivates and engages students in individualized learning. It is in lieu of this, that learners' exposure to various social media such as YouTube, MySpace, facebook, Digg, and Artificial Intelligence (Ai), appears to be of great assistance to what they learn in and out of school (Zhang and Olfman, 2010).

In all of these, educational technology refers to the use of media and equipment in the teaching - learning process. These instructional materials include chalkboard, flannel boards, models and overhead projectors. Technology in education implies video/audio cassette recorder, video cassette, player/recorder, radio, television, telephone and computer. In addition to this, educational technology can be seen as the application of the principles of technology in solving educational problems. Therefore, the use of computers in education is traceable to the development of educational technology. The objective of the national policy on computer education launched in 1988 was specifically to expose the learners to:

- (i) Knowledge of computers and their uses in everyday life;
 - (ii) The use of computers to facilitate or enhance their learning process and problem solving and;
 - (iii) Acquire and develop rudimentary skills like data processing, word processing, record keeping and financial analysis.
- Notably, computer education programme was planned to improve the quality of teaching-learning in schools aiding technological and socio -economic development of a nation. Technology in education no doubt equips the recipient with the ability to utilize the computer and other digital electronic devices for the purpose of transmitting information technology (IT) from one place to the other.

Abdellatif (2014) opined that teaching and learning are integrated circles which focuses on what both teachers and students do in class or outside the classroom (reading for learning). Although, one could sometimes happen without the other. In any way, teaching and learning are two sides of the same coin, so to say. The duo concepts involve the use of strategies which maximize opportunities for interaction in class. The ultimate aim of teaching is to bring about learning via the use of technology. Therefore, a teaching process that does not result in learning is of no use. Without quality teaching, only a limited form of learning is possible. This of course is no surprised that the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) states that "No education system can rise above the quality of its teachers". In some American states, employers even use students' academic achievement as part of the criterion for deciding teachers' performance.

Teaching thus connotes imparting knowledge or skill while learning refers to acquisition of knowledge by updating his/her data and the learner's feedback (Judeh, 2014). The goal achievement of students in the school is reflected in excellent performance. Performance in this study encompasses the full range of activities that would characterize a school as being successful. This would, in addition to students' academic performance furthermore include well motivated and committed teachers, learner satisfaction and involvement, parental involvement, a clean orderly school environment, qualitative teaching and learning process and strong principal leadership ability. Although, assessment of teaching and learning in Nigeria has not been sufficiently done. Sometimes, only learning is assessed while teaching is left out and vice versa.

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In such a situation, it is impossible to have comprehensive data and plausible generalizations about the teaching and learning trends in the school system. There are however, few good learning assessments that tried to ascertain altogether the impact of teachers, school administration, parents and environment on the learning outcome of students to show that all these factors count. This being the case, the major concern of schools is the success or effectiveness of teaching and learning process using any appropriate means available. Though, performance is determined by many other factors just as technology is the focus of this paper. Notably, there are many teaching methods that is available to practising teachers; quick meaning of this is that teaching methods have received different classifications from different teachers. In all fields and to all teachers, the most appropriate method of teaching therefore is that which can motivate the students and sustain their interest in the course of instruction. It is equally important to note that teaching methods also involves the interaction of the teachers, learners and the subject matter.

Learning on the other hand, has a close connection with teaching because when there is one who is teaching there are students who are learning. Learning is thus a change in behaviour of learners as a result of interaction with environment and a purpose to fulfil had become a necessity. Any activity can be called learning so far as it develops the individual (in any respect, good or bad) and makes him alter behaviour and experiences different from what they would otherwise have been” (Woodworth in Ali and Masih, 2021). Quality learning is extensive, integrative, and generative (Lawson and Kirby, 2012). Based on their studies, they observed that three factors influence the quality of learning. These are dispositions towards learning, conditions for learning, and the learning process.

The learning process is much associated with the approaches to learning. For decades, one of the most persistent problems which teachers have struggled to solve has been how to achieve maximum results with minimum but effective medium of instruction. There has been a need to change our emphasis on teaching by the teacher to learning by the learner. Thus, rather than be a teacher - centred activity, instruction has become learner - centred. Teachers need to ascertain what their students wish to know and how it is relevant to their life and work and how they learn best. Hence, for effective teaching and learning to take place, there must be a correlation between teacher’s instructional strategies and students’ learning styles (Akinbobola, 2011b).

Application of Technology at the Secondary Schools

Schools all over the world are increasingly turning their attention to different kinds of technological resources to support and enhance the teaching and learning of the 21st century skills. This is especially so because technological skills have become critical in our daily lives and more importantly, at the secondary schools. These skills are needed for success in our rapidly changing and highly competitive world. Thomas (2004) and Ranga (2004) classified the application of computers and other communication technologies in education into three broad categories: Pedagogy, Training and Continuing Education. The pedagogical applicability of the ICTs is about learning with the support of various components of computer. This perhaps could be the starting point for secondary school leavers before gaining admission into the Universities or teacher training college. Olakulehin (2007) on his part emphasized that pedagogy application of ICTs involves effective learning with the aid of computers and other information technologies, serving the purpose of learning aids, which plays complementary roles in teaching/learning situations rather than supplements the teacher. This means that ICTs can facilitate learning in secondary schools and individualized learning through methods like modeling, simulation and so on.

Obviously, the effective application of ICTs has advantage of increasing the learners’ motivation to learn more and desirable attitudes towards actualizing more of ICTs tools. The evolution of mobile technology has also put learning in the palms of both teachers and their learners. Mobile technology refers to mobile devices that include Personal Digital Assistance (PDA), tablets, digital cell phones and ipods. They are self-effacing enough that they have become useful in implementing different learning techniques and pedagogies (Dale and Povey, 2007; Varis, 2007; Arkorful, Oduro and Abaidoo, 2016). Mobile technology learning, otherwise called M-learning is learning achieved through wireless technology devices that can be pocketed and utilized wherever the learner’s device can receive unbroken transmission signals (Attewell and Savil - Smith 2005). Apparently, it is no more sufficient for teachers to use a particular technology or software where students’ need constant assess to an evolving array of technological tools and activities that will enable them to engage in problem-solving, decision-making, teamwork/collaboration and innovation. The followings can be used or designated to perform the under-listed activities that hitherto promotes teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools in the 21st Century.

Audio and video devices such as radios, television programmes, DVD, VCD have been in use in the classroom for a long time. Technologies of the 21st century now allow teachers to stream audio over the internet. There are also webcasts and podcasts available over the internet for students and teachers to download. Websites like Youtube also allow teachers and

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students opportunity to watch on-line videos. Messaging programs such as Skype, Adobe Connect or webcams are used by teachers to interact with guest speakers and other experts.

1. **Blogging:** These are personal internet journals which allow both students and teachers to post their thoughts, ideas and comments on the website for others to comment on, open discussion or seek opinions. Blogging allows students and teachers to share their thoughts and comments on the thoughts of others thus creating an interactive learning environment (Courts and Tucker, 2012) on-line even when separated by distance.
2. **Webcam** which are video cameras that streams images through the computer network which could be webcasted to create virtual platforms, In this environment, teachers can give instructions and receive feedback from students.
3. **Screen casting:** This is a recent trend that allows users to share their screens directly from their browser online so that the viewers can stream the video directly. By this means user can follow the individual's line of thought without ambiguities associated with explanations.
4. **Artificial intelligence (AI):** This involves the use of computer to produce simulations of intelligent behaviours in robots to perform tasks usually performed by intelligent humans.

Benefits of Technology at the Secondary Schools in Nigeria

The 21st century world is a dynamic one, one that is ever changing and surrounded by information. It is therefore important that the type of education given to students should match the dynamic nature of the world. Technology in teaching has many benefits especially to students in secondary schools. The following are some of the benefits of technology in education.

Collaboration of knowledge:

The employment of technology in the classroom is important as it allows secondary school students share knowledge among themselves anywhere, anytime. The use of technology in secondary schools allowed knowledge mobility, this means that knowledge can be gotten, shared and used anywhere, anytime within the classroom and outside the classroom. This collaborative learning can be between teachers and students or within students.

Student Centered:

Using technology in training as well as learning procedure makes teaching transcends beyond the traditional notion of the teacher being the sole custodian of knowledge. With the use of technological gadgets like the internet, secondary school students can access to any information they need and also learn at their own pace. Ajayi (2008) posited that training as well as learning has evolved passed the teacher positioning himself in front of a collection of students as well as circulating information to them without the students' adequate participation. This harnesses the point that technology in education makes teaching and learning less teacher - centered and more student - centered.

Convenience:

It makes educational activities easy and simple. With this blended method of teaching, students do not necessarily need to carry heavy backpacks, they can easily read and store information in their laptops, do exercise and send to their teachers at any time. Also, teachers do not need to carry scripts around as students works can be marked with the aid of technological devices. Technology in education no doubt is convenient for the trainers and the pupils as well.

Wider range of information:

The internet houses a lot of information; thus, students can get more information about a subject area beyond the one they get from their textbooks. Through sites Like the Research Gate, Google scholar, Google and others, students has a wider range of access to informative information about different subjects.

Intensifies Teaching:

ICT gives room for students to learn intensively and thoroughly. Through audiovisual materials, students have a more concrete idea about the concepts they being taught. For instance if students are taught about how the intestines work and they get to only see a picture of the intestine, they may get an abstract view of how the intestines really are, but with the help of the YouTube, students can see and even watch how the intestines functions, this has helped in intensifying the lesson the teacher has taught, with this students will not forget this concept easily, they will also be no need of memorizing because what they have seen will stick better.

Updated knowledge:

With the employment of technology in secondary school education, students are exposed to recent and updated knowledge about certain subjects instead of the old information in most textbooks. Studies to ascertain the academic potentials and benefits of mobile application, have shown that apart from its benefits as a learning tool, learners vocabulary are improved,

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same as their understanding of content/concepts, students are also motivated to do well and prepared for class than their counterparts who do not use or have them (Wylie, 2016).

Challenges of Using Technology at the Secondary Schools in Nigeria

The integration and use of modern technology in the nation's post primary schools was a sought of relief to the former traditional method which has vogue for decades. As complex, portable, convenient and fascinating as the modern technology is, there are still setbacks which includes:

1. Inadequate training of teachers: It has been observed that these new technique of teaching - learning has brought about huge demand on personnel training and re-training so as to ensure its effective integration in the classroom. This training will enable the teachers to use software programmes to stimulate students to improve upon the under developed skills in a variety of content areas.
2. The use of technology in the classroom is capital intensive and only few schools can afford such equipments as computers, internet and so on.
3. It is time consuming: Much time is needed for the implementation of technology in the classrooms which may not be available.
4. The quality of computer or digital cameras for classrooms are grossly inadequate.
5. Malfunctions of computer: Reacting to the malfunctioning of computer Osasebor and Okunsebor (2009) said that one of the major disadvantages of the application of computers in the Nigerian education is due to system malfunctioning which can be experienced in the computer itself. They added that computer in education depends largely on electricity and without it, it cannot function. Irregular supply of power has been a great problem to the use of computers in the classroom.
6. Absence of electricity in rural areas hinders the use of computer technology in the classroom in such locations.

Conclusion

The world today is powered by technology in virtually all areas of life and sectors of the economy. Education that is provided in any nation is to empower the citizens to fit successfully into their society. The 21st century world is ruled by information. Only individuals with the ability and skills to utilize modern digital tools to access and generate information and knowledge can and will perform in the global work space and platform. The technologies of today have completely changed the platform for learning. Students now learn from different sources. Teachers need to key into the modern learning modes by utilizing the tools offered by the digital revolution to prepare learners who are globally empowered. The idea of a fixed classroom where students learn only in the presence of their teachers and from what the teacher provides for them has gone long before now. Learners can now learn with the teachers directing even when they are separated by time and distance. This type of learning, apart from its efficacy in promoting self-paced learning, motivates learners to engage in research and dissemination of knowledge as fast as possible which are connected to networking and collaboration. To remain relevant therefore, teachers and students should keep abreast with the learning technologies of the time through re-engineering and innovating in system structure, perceptual change, instructional, administrative and assessment practices that are compliant with the 21st Century literacy skills.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been put forward in this paper:

1. The need for adequate training of teachers and students (or learners) have become imperative in the 21st Century.
2. Appropriate machinery should be put in place to ensure that computers and its accessories are provided to schools via loan or subsidized rates for those who can pay at once. Checks should also be put in place to ensure they are not sold when in need of cash by those given.
3. Issue of allocation of more time to school programmes and activities be looked into. This is in fact a serious matter aimed at ensuring all that needed to be learnt is learn.
4. Adequate supply and maintenance of computers in schools be looked into. This can be done periodically and avoid if necessary that such is not a conduit pipe to amass wealth by those at the helms of affairs.
5. Alternative power supply to schools be massively invested on. This is especially as public electricity supply in the Country can no longer be relied upon.

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